

Project Management Group Meeting – Wednesday 23rd March 2011

Final Minutes

Welcome and Introduction

Dennis Jensen opened the meeting and welcomed everyone to the Danish Ministry of Agriculture and to Copenhagen. The project management group (PMG) were informed that Dennis Jensen and Niels Gøtke have formally changed Ministry and from DFIA to DASTI and have taken the responsibilities of EUPHRECO with them.

In attendance was Martine Maes (ILVO), Dennis Jensen (DASTI), Elspeth Steel (Fera), Alan Inman (Fera), Pilar Sabuquillo (INIA) Sylvia Bluemel (AGES), Alois Egartner (AGES), Elfriede Fuhrmann (BMLFUW), Jens Unger (JKI), Silke Steinmüller (JKI), Leonor Cruz (INRB), Steen Lykke Nielsen (Aarhus University) and Eric Regouin (EL&I).

The main focus of the PMG meeting was final preparations of the kick-off (KO) meeting. Everybody agreed that the most important considerations were the integration of the new partners, the involvement of all partners in the responsibilities of the project, highlighting the achievements of EUPHRESCO and listing the success criteria for EUPHRESCO 2. As well as KO meeting and WP5 workshop preparations the PMG discussed each WP and related issues. The objectives of each WP as set out in the description of work were briefly summarised and have been included below.

WP2: Implementing, testing and refining the long-term self-sustainable network structure

Objectives:

WP2 aims to implement, test and refine the proposed model network structure and *modus operandi* from the current EUPHRESCO project. The overall aim is to ensure that the EUPHRESCO network can continue in a durable and self-sustainable way after 2013, in order to deliver effective transnational research coordination and collaboration in support of the Community Plant Health Regime. Further, it aims to build confidence and experience in the network's management structures, *modus operandi*, processes and tools that are needed to implement transnational research, thereby demonstrating the added value and benefits of involvement in the network. The work will consolidate and build on the success of previous EUPHRESCO-1's outputs and establish a culture of collaboration and a regular network routine.

The main objectives are:

- To implement and establish the proposed (from EUPHRESCO-1) structure and *modus operandi* of the long-term self-sustainable network.
- To evaluate and refine the structure and *modus operandi* of the long-term network of funders to ensure that a strong, long-lasting and self-sustainable network emerges.
- To maintain ongoing core network activities that underpin transnational research coordination and collaboration, e.g. mapping activities and database updating; dissemination of transnational research outputs; advising on plant health research priorities in FP7; maintaining linkages to key stakeholders; maintaining the EUPHRESCO toolbox.

Silke Steinmüller and Jens Unger (the WP2 leaders) told the group that it was important that new partners and observers understand the expectations of the projects and these expectations should be set at the right level, neither too high nor too low. They also told the group that it was important

for all partners new and old and observers to be involved in WP2 from the onset. The PMG agreed and added that as many people as possible should be involved in all the WPs. The PMG felt it was important to engage all partners into the working groups and spent some time discussing the best way to do this. They felt that the KO meeting would provide a good opportunity to sign partners up to working groups for each WP.

Action: New partners will be asked to check the future network *modus operandi* and asked if they could use it and if they are happy with it. New partners need to be reassured that the work and time required will not be onerous. The project itself is for 3 years and the network (with less administration) will only require a year's engagement.

WP 3: Deepening through transnational research projects

Objectives:

WP3 aims to deepen the European plant health research network cooperation by delivering new transnational research activities, especially coordinated or jointly-funded research projects. These will further support the development and implementation of plant health policy and improve the phytosanitary science base in Europe. Such joint research activities will build additional confidence and experience in joint transnational research commissioning and demonstrate the added value and benefits that result.

The main WP objectives are:

- To identify, prioritise and select transnational research topics suitable for cooperation and collaboration, especially jointly-funded projects, including consultation with current key stakeholders and advisors.
- To initiate transnational research collaborations to support EU plant health policy, operations and science capability.

Alois Egartner and Sylvia Bluemel gave the group a brief progress update on the work they had carried out so far for WP3 and also informed the group of their proposed agenda for the WP3 session. Alois Egartner first presentation will be followed by a short topic workshop. The KO meeting will be asked to give topic suggestions. In order to facilitate this exercise the meeting will be provided with the EPPO alert list, folders with annexes of quarantine pests Directives and a memo of the criteria for choosing topics. A very quick eligibility check will take place towards the end of the workshop.

Eric mentioned that he has money available in 2011 to put into a real common pot; he will bring it up during Sylvia's presentation during the KO meeting. He also raised his interest in having a 'communications' project about communicating risks to the wider public; plant breeders, nurseries, plant buyers etc. Sylvia thought that European funds would be available for this type of public relations work. Alan agreed to send information on ongoing projects to Eric. The PMG felt that communication should be better defined; e.g. who are we communicating to and what are we communicating. Sylvia thought that currently available information should be checked; Eric agreed to do some background research. Does the right information reach the right people to serve the right purpose?

WP4: Deepening through improved processes and tools for transnational cooperation

Objectives:

The overall aim of WP4 is to develop and enhance approaches for a 'market place' for funders that better facilitates and strengthens transnational cooperation in phytosanitary research. The platform will enable information exchanged between funders and/or scientists. It will facilitate faster identification of common priorities, faster coordination of joint expertise and better exploitation of

both reference material and specialised facilities. Outputs of this workpackage will feed directly back into WP3 and support and facilitate ongoing transnational activities.

The main WP objectives are:

- To develop improved technical possibilities (platforms and processes) for operating and enhancing the virtual phytosanitary 'market place' where common research needs of funders are identified and prioritised and where easier access to specialised expertise, reference material and specialised facilities is realised. Funders with similar needs join forces and transnational research projects can then be initiated to better address these needs. This will include improving, adapting and developing the existing use of the EUPHRESKO website as a key tool for the market place.
- To facilitate easy exchange and rapid access to information and knowledge between National Plant Protection Organisations, the research establishment, EU bodies, e.g. SANCO, EFSA, and other relevant international institutions, e.g. EPPO.
- To create more opportunities and to explore new and creative ways of delivering transnationally funded research that addresses plant health policy, operations and science questions. One particular motivation to develop such enhanced possibilities is the need to react quickly to problems (creation of an emergency track for initiating plant health research, both with regard to the procedure and the funds available).
- To enhance the potential for transnational research commissioning by identifying specific national barriers to funding collaborations and by exploring strategies to overcome these barriers.
- To explore and enhance linkages to other key stakeholders (both at national and transnational levels) for improved agenda setting and research collaboration, and enhance linkages to plant health activities and coordination mechanisms.

Alois informed the group about software systems such as Adobe Connect Pro (temporary chat room). That could be explored for future use on the website for topic selection and interest expression. The PMG agreed that the website needed to be updated and needed to be made more user-friendly.

Actions:

- Elspeth Steel agreed to take charge of the updating and will ask all partners to provide their contact details for the website, they will need to provide their institute's logos, web address and contact person details.
- Elspeth will also ensure that the toolbox is put on the public area of the website as soon as possible.
- Elspeth and Alan will update the text on the EUPHRESKO website in preparation for a re-launch to take place by the end of April.

Eric Regouin informed the group that he will introduce the partners to WP4 by working through the four thematic areas and go through the 13 deliverables. Eric informed the group that he would like to take the opportunity of the KO meeting to engage as many partners as possible in these deliverables. Partners will need to have some indication of the time they will have to spend on them. Also, some deliverables need input from all partners such as barriers for transnational research.

WP5: Enlarging the network cooperation

Objectives:

WP5 will aim to increase and encourage the involvement of additional organisations with an interest in transnational research collaborations (e.g. new partners, observers and others). It will broaden the potential cooperation of the network, especially regionally within Europe, more internationally (third countries) and in some previously under-represented sectors (e.g. forestry plant health).

Expanding EUPHRESKO's links more internationally will provide research opportunities that will help support the Community Plant Health Regime. In particular, wider international cooperation would enable research on quarantine pests to be done in their countries of origin. International cooperation may be both at the programme level (between national funders) or at the project level (inclusion of more research providers from non-European countries within transnational projects).

The main WP objectives are:

- To attract and integrate more EU member states, associated countries and third countries, e.g. selected International Cooperation Partners Countries (ICPC's) into the EUPHRESKO network.
- To explore opportunities and, if relevant, implement regionally-based transnational plant health research (i.e. on specific regionally-based crops or pest issues) and sector-based (plant production sectors, e.g. forestry plant health) under-represented in EUPHRESKO-1.
- To explore possibilities and implement, as appropriate, collaborations with third countries, including some ICPC's and developed countries, with similar plant health problems as EU to EUPHRESKO-2.
- To explore possibilities and, if possible, implement collaborations with certain third countries (e.g. ICPC's) which are currently sources of plant quarantine pests of concern to the EU.

No specific WP5 issues were raised, Steen Lykke Nielsen emphasised the importance of integrating the new partners as much as possible into the project. He told the group that he had arranged for all the new partners to give a 5 minute presentation to introduce themselves, their institutes and their national plant health programmes to the network.

The group agreed that the next PMG meeting should be planned for September 2011.

Action: Elspeth agreed to coordinate the arrangements for the next PMG meeting in September.

No other business was raised and Alan closed the meeting.